

Basic Technical Movement Skills of Young Belt Wrestlers

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Abstract: The training of belt wrestlers consists of basic technical and tactical movements. This article studies the types of technical movements and movement skills of belt wrestlers.

Keywords: Belt wrestling, offensive and defensive movements, competition, opponent, defense, competition, deceptive movements, stance.

INTRODUCTION

The training movements of belt wrestlers are those movements that are allowed by the rules of the competition and ensure the success of offensive and defensive movements. In a belt wrestler, these include reconnaissance, seeing the opponent's weaknesses, maneuvering, and the movements and position of their own plans.

Intelligence is a set of actions aimed at obtaining external and internal information about the belt wrestler's opponent, his physical structure, characteristics, qualities, capabilities and condition: about the style of the competition - active or passive, offensive or defensive, about his favorite movements, thoughts, etc.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

It is especially important for a belt wrestler to determine what his opponent's favorite stance is during the competition, at what distance he stands, what technique he uses and their strength, how he prepares for a technique, his intentions, how he attacks, defends and counterattacks, what his strength, agility and endurance are. Intelligence can be carried out with real and fake movements of a more preparatory nature and with the use of the belt wrestler's favorite techniques.

A belt wrestler should be a psychologist during the competition, knowing the opponent's condition; Physiologist - knowing the opponent's condition based on his movements, breathing and sweating: he must be an artist, a brave, strong-willed athlete who deceives the opponent with false movements, misleads him from using the correct technique, forces his plan on the opponent, and thus firmly implements his plan and achieves victory.

In competitive conditions, using a trick against the opponent to raise the image of the competition is to create favorable conditions and take preparatory actions in order to successfully apply the technique, choose a convenient moment for defense and counterattack. Tricks can be used in different positions and at different distances, using deceptive movements and false movements, using the method of encouragement, suggestion, as well as using offensive and defensive movements to carry out the selected technique or counterattack. With trickery, a belt wrestler tries to take the initiative, show activity, choose a convenient place in

the ring for the necessary action, and sometimes try to escape from his opponent.

In order to hide their true intentions from their opponent, to lose their vigilance, to distract him and to carry out their planned plan, their movements and posture are masked. In masking movements, experienced athletes show their opponents that they are calm and passive, some are relaxed and suddenly exert all their strength, some express their passion like a talented artist. They wave their hands, others show themselves calm, relaxed or confident before a belt fight, etc. Each belt fighter has his own unique style of masking. Therefore, sometimes it is very difficult to determine whether his intentions are true or false.

Basic technical skills of young belt wrestlers

Technical movements of belt wrestlers in competitions are the decisive offensive movements, defense, protection and counterattack movements against the opponent. Simple attack methods in the attack, that is, they perform their movements more quickly, which solves the tactical task.

Complex attack methods and movements of a belt wrestler in the attack - these can consist of various combinations performed in two stages, combined with deception, fake movements.

Defensive methods and movements of a belt wrestler - these are defensive and counterattack movements. Defensive movements include: the opponent's methods used in the attack, getting rid of the attack or avoiding it by using counter techniques.

The first type - movements according to a strict program of actions: in this case, the athlete plans in advance to "catch" his opponent while he is performing a certain technique. To do this, he waits for the moment to come and does not recognize other options for the opportunity to attack.

Athletes of the second type have several "pre-prepared" tactical actions as an initial "model".

The actions of athletes of the third type are more deliberate: they do not think through the decisive path in advance and act depending on the situation that has arisen, the actions of the opponent.

In order not to get attached to the actions of the opponent and to immediately use the moment prepared for his decisive attack without interruption, it is necessary to train belt wrestlers of the fourth type to prepare the dynamic situation, that is, to create a favorable situation for the attack in advance.

It is necessary to educate belt wrestlers in a psychological direction aimed at activating actions. This work is carried out in order to create a favorable dynamic situation for the attack and use this situation to gain an advantage and victory. Knowing the favorable dynamic situations that arise during belt wrestling and being ready to perform technical movements and attacks in a timely manner reflects only one aspect of psychological orientation. Psychological orientation to prepare and use a favorable dynamic situation for the upbringing of a highly qualified modern belt wrestler must be based on good physical and technical preparation, that is, the belt wrestler must be ready for non-stop active movements throughout the belt wrestling.

The athlete's ability to correctly and timely prepare for the upcoming competition in a highly emotional mood, taking into account the strengths and weaknesses of his opponent, is of great importance for victory. Only with the help of a great spirit can one develop strength to the maximum.

The increasing competition in sports competitions places great demands on athletes not only in terms of physical and technical preparation, but also in terms of their ability to manage their emotional state in the conditions of responsible competitions.

The tense situation in competitions, negative emotions, and many objective and subjective obstacles that arise during the competition can become a powerful factor that significantly reduces tactical skills for belt wrestlers.

Special studies have made it possible to observe the level of emotional excitement of belt wrestlers on the eve of the competition and on the day of the competition, as well as changes in emotional tension during competitions.

A significant increase in excitement is observed in belt wrestlers while waiting for the results of the draw, and a significant decrease after the results are announced.

Matches with weaker opponents in the first round of competitions are clearly noticeable in belt wrestlers.

The excitement of the athletes who had to meet the main opponents in the first round also increased. The ability of belt wrestlers to control their emotional state during participation in competitions reduces the impact of negative emotions on the competitive spirit and makes it possible to achieve high sports results.

The special physical training of a wrestler is aimed at developing the movement qualities in strict accordance with the requirements set by the characteristics of the wrestler's competitive activity. The special physical training of wrestlers is carried out mainly on the wrestling mat and is aimed at developing the most important movement qualities in the composition of movement skills. Therefore, competition exercises involving various possible complexities are used as the main means of special physical training. Such complicated exercises enhance the impact on the wrestler's body. For example, throwing a partner in a heavier weight category, training competitions are performed with the replacement of partners, etc.

All these exercises allow you to develop one or another mechanism of energy supply, have a comprehensive effect on the wrestler's training and at the same time increase his physical and technical-tactical readiness. All the listed types of physical training are inextricably linked. Insufficient attention to any type of physical training during training will ultimately prevent the development of sports skills. Therefore, it is very important to observe the optimal ratio of the listed types of physical training during training.

CONCLUSION

The literature on wrestling includes a huge number of theoretical and practical training methods, which indicates the large amount of work done in this area. It has become clear from the literature that, despite the abundance of scientific and methodological foundations, the level of load volume and intensity ratios for low-skilled athletes who are just starting training has not been sufficiently studied. In order to truly accelerate the training process, it is important not only to know the volume and intensity of loads at different stages of training, but also to know the method and art of using basic training parameters, taking into account the different ratios of wrestlers' movements. As can be seen from the analysis of the literature, experiments on the results of wrestlers and the ratio of movement abilities have not been conducted. Serious study and application of these topical issues in practice will be effective in training wrestlers in children's and youth sports schools.

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